

QUIZ**LAST NAME: KASHGARY****FIRST NAME: ADEL****PROGRAM CODE: DIFE****COURSE CODE: ACA- 401D****PERIOD NUMBER: QUIZ****INSTRUCTOR: Pr. CLEENEWERCK**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium.

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2019 on Windows 10)

1. Which one of the following is true about the aims of a good essay?

- Persuade readers of an idea based on evidence¹**
- It should not try to present or discuss something
- It should not include relevant examples
- Give less time to read, research, think, and write

2. Before writing an essay, each paragraph should contain:

- Topic sentence, supporting sentences, and proper name format
- Evidence
- Topic with supporting sentences, evidence, and analysis²**
- Title, a text page, footnotes, and references

¹ “ACA-401D PERIOD 1 - Course pack” n.d., 2.

² “ACA-401D PERIOD 1 - Course pack” n.d., 4.

3. **Readers will expect writers to use different levels of sources, called primary, secondary, and:**

- Tertiary³**
- Encyclopedias
- World wide web pages
- None of the above

4. **The scholarly or professional periodicals available primarily in academic libraries and by subscription described as:**

- Journals Articles⁴**
- Magazine Articles
- Unpublished Sources
- Public Documents

5. **Data is defined as:**

- Original materials on which other research is based
- Online indexes that usually include abstracts for each primary or secondary resource, and may also include a digital copy of the resource
- Print media, such as books, brochures, journals, magazines, newspapers, and books

³ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 110.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 110.

Facts and information⁵

6. **Research (***) resembles an amiable conversation in which you and your imagined readers reason together to solve a problem whose solution they do not yet fully accept:**

Objective

Aim

Argument⁶

Offer

7. **The subject of inquiry around a particular research problem that the study will address:**

Topic⁷

Dissertation

Research

Thesis

8. **Which of the following's elements might be the content of an abstract?**

Research problem or issue that was addressed⁸

⁵ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 15.

⁶ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 36.

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 31.

- The theoretical basis that guided the study**
 - Key findings, conclusions, and recommendations**
 - Appendices
9. **As specified in Article 288 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, they comprise chiefly:**
- Directives
 - Decisions and regulations only
 - Directives
 - Regulations & decisions but directives are binding but not directly applicable⁹**
10. **Commission's and the EU's traditional dealings with non-member countries in the fields of trade, aid and various forms of cooperation refers to which of the below terms:**
- External relations¹⁰**
 - European Union
 - EU Non-member countries
 - European Free Trade Association

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 168.

⁹ *English Style Guide*, Seventh Edition (European Commission Directorate-General for Translation, 2011), 62.

¹⁰ *English Style Guide*, Seventh Edition (European Commission Directorate-General for Translation, 2011), 81.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.